

Understanding the Manifold Gap for RSE Recognition in National Laboratories

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Abstract – Research Software Engineer (RSE) is an emerging career track which is gaining traction in various parts of the world. This paper makes a case for the need for RSE recognition in U.S. DOE national laboratories. The paper lists the current status of software engineers in research with respect to the various career tracks and titles they have. The paper also discusses and delves into implications that the RSE recognition may potentially have on different factors related to the individual growth, job training, mentoring, career advancement, among other things – in a national lab environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Software development is now an integral part of computational science research being done at U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) national laboratories. Over the decades with the emergence of supercomputers, software being developed by these organizations has ranged over a wide spectrum, from quick-prototype code to software that is production-ready and runs on extreme-scale machines in leadership computing facilities. Thus, considering the importance of software in today's computational science research, almost all research teams require some degree of software engineering expertise to be able to communicate intelligently and function competitively.

Compared to industry-based software developers, who work on product-focused software, work done by software developers in research organizations differs significantly, typically focusing on open-ended research that is arguably more challenging. Over the years, growing effort is making this vast distinction more visible. The concept of Research Software Engineer (RSE)[1][2] has emerged, with the RSE movement gaining momentum worldwide. This paper makes a case for the need for RSE recognition in U.S. DOE national laboratories. It attempts to outline the gaps that exists due to the non-recognition of the RSE career track – which impacts several factors related to career

titles/tracks, training, mentorship, career advancement, appreciation and recognition – for a software engineer.

II. CAREER TRACKS AND TITLES

The concept of software developers working in research is well-known in national laboratories. This concept is, however, implemented under various and sometimes ambiguous position titles and tracks—that is, an amalgamation of position titles used to describe traditional industry software developers, academic postdoctoral candidates, or lab staff scientists. For example, the following position titles are used at Argonne National Laboratory in computer science and computational science domains: software engineer, software development specialist, computational engineer, computational engineering specialist, research software specialist. Related titles, where work includes activities in domains of math, chemistry, physics, or other areas of computational science, include: project specialist in computational science, application performance engineer, applied mathematics specialist, experimental systems engineer, experimental systems specialist etc.

The plethora of position titles related to research software engineering work in national laboratories gives rise to ambiguity and sometimes indicates an unclear career track for software engineers. The various position titles come with different metrics for future career progression and promotions. Depending on the title and organization, the metrics may include software developed, publications, citations, funding obtained, proposal contributions, indications of domestic and international community standing, work with software users, etc. A wide variety in titles as well as differing career tracks can lead to confusion among software developers with regard to future career progression. This gap could be filled to a large degree by adoption of the Research Software Engineer track.

III. EDUCATION AND TRAINING

Recognition of the RSE track would also lead to a more streamlined onboarding process for teams working in national labs. One challenge for most projects is a continuous influx of new contributors, who are expected already to have technical domain expertise or to learn these skills on the fly as needed by the job. While most teams try to provide mentoring to new members, limited resources require that newcomers be fairly independent and proactive in learning new technical aspects. Candidates hired for these multiple position titles, spread across various divisions and groups, come from all over the domain (industry, universities) and various countries. Such a variety of candidates and career tracks limits an organization's ability to provide streamlined technical training across the board. A clear and identified RSE track would help to define training prerequisites for such candidates. Gaps in knowledge could be more easily filled through standardized and proven training programs, and teams within a division as well as across an organization could share training tools and resources.

RSE's differ dramatically from other software engineers in terms of knowledge expectations. Most RSEs would (arguably) be required to be familiar not only with programming languages but also advanced topics such as software development lifecycles, software interoperability, revision control systems, build systems, reproducibility, refactoring, continuous integration testing, and performance portability, as well as to have comfort in communicating with domain-specific researchers. An influx of M.S/Ph.D. candidates from universities is fairly common in national laboratories. Identifying a clear RSE track would allow prospective candidates as well as their educational institutes to prepare knowledgeably for research software engineering careers.

IV. MENTORSHIP AND ADVANCEMENT

Another manifestation of multiple titles and tracks for software engineers in research labs has been the lack of mentorship to software engineers. Software engineers usually form a smaller fraction of the organization compared to other staff (scientists, post-docs, etc.). Mentorship is likely more easily available for post-doctoral candidates and scientist-track employees in national laboratories, since these tracks are clearly defined and solidified. However, this is not the case for software engineers. Oftentimes, it is difficult to map

mentor-mentee partnerships, and seeking a mentor across divisions may be even more challenging despite having spent years in an organization, due to the variability of position titles. Having a streamlined RSE track would encourage identification of peers across the organization and encourage building healthy mentor-mentee relationships.

V. APPRECIATION AND RECOGNITION

Multiple titles and career tracks for software engineers performing similar jobs essentially dilutes the concentration of software engineers in an organization. Such a dilution makes comparison of capabilities and achievements of various employees difficult, possibly resulting in a perception of under-appreciation of valuable employees and higher attrition rates in teams and organizations. Attrition leads to offboarding, onboarding, and training costs, as well as delayed schedules and deliverables. Recognition of employees, beyond a paycheck, is important to create a positive working environment. Having a standardized RSE career track would help to overcome these issues to a great degree.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this position paper, we make a case for the need for RSE recognition in U.S. DOE national laboratories. RSE recognition, if adopted by national laboratories, will impact software engineers working in research, in multitude ways. The paper focused on some such improvements, ranging from growth, job training, mentoring, career advancement, appreciation and recognition – in a national lab environment.

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REFERENCES

- [1] "The Research Software Engineer," R. Baxter, N. C. Hong, D. Gorissen et al. In the Digital Research Conference, Oxford, 2012, pp. 1–3.
- [2] "A Not-So-Brief History of Research Software Engineers," S. Hettrick. Available online at: <https://www.software.ac.uk/blog/2016-08-17-not-so-brief-history-research-software-engineers-0>. Accessed 2020-Nov-03.